

CERTAIN DERIVATIVES OF 4-AMINODIPHENYLSULPHONES

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The preparation of certain acyl derivatives and Schiff's bases from 2 : 5-dihydroxy-4-amino- and 4-aminomethyldiphenylsulphone, as well as, from 2 : 4-dinitro-4'-aminodiphenylsulphone derivatives, has been described.

It is now generally believed that though the activity of common sulfa drugs depends to a considerable degree on the concentration of ionic form present in any condition, the drug action is brought about by combination of the drug through its basic amino group with some enzyme system of the organism (cf. Klotz, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 66, 459; Wood, *Brit. J. Exp. Path.*, 1940, 21, 74). It is difficult to approach the problem rationally as no definite knowledge on all enzyme systems of the micro-organism nor that of the host is yet known. The available evidence favours the view that a sulfa drug acts by displacement of *p*-aminobenzoic acid from an active centre in an enzyme surface, or, by simply competing with it for the formation of the enzyme complex. For this, presence of one free amino group would suffice, as even in sulphone groups the monoaminodiphenylsulphone derivatives are also being found to be active in comparison with diaminodiphenylsulphone (cf. Mingoia and Berti, *Chem. Abs.*, 1945, 39, 2057; Bauer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 2254; U. S. P. 2399600). Substitution of the amino group by a suitable grouping may again help in the isolation of a product that can acquire the property of forming an enzyme-drug complex at the site of infection. As a matter of fact, since the observations of Buttle (*Lancet*, 1937, p. 1331) and Fourneau (*Bull. Acad. Med.*, 1937, 110, 210) that *pp*-diaminodiphenylsulphone exerts a strong anti-streptococcal activity, several derivatives of the compound have been prepared which are found to be of promise even against leprosy and tuberculosis (Barry and McNalley, *Nature*, 1945, 156, 48; Callomon and Raiziss, *Ann. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1946, 53, 374; Youmann *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1946, 54, 295; Brownlee, *Lancet*, 1948, *ii*, p. 131; Muir, *Trans. Roy. Soc. Trop. Med. Hyg.*, 1948, 41, 5, 575). Recently we also noticed (*Science & Culture*, 1949, 14, 339) that certain dihydroxyaminosulphones exhibit a bacteristatic activity against *E. typhosa* and *V. Cholerae* *in vitro*. But this type of activity is completely unreliable guide for the discovery of compounds with activity *in vivo* (cf. Hoggarth and Martin, *Brit. J. Pharm. & Chem.*, 1948 3, 146). The chemistry of these and some

other new sulphone derivatives, since prepared, has, however, been recorded in the body of this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of 4'-Acetaminodiphenylsulphones.—To a hot solution of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinic acid ("Org. Syntheses", Vol. V, p. 1) or *p*-acetaminomethylbenzene sulphinic acid (cf. Sikdar and Basu, this *journal*, 1945, 22, 343) in water was added a molar amount of *p*-benzoquinone in water and the mixture was well shaken for half an hour and left aside. Crystals separating were crystallised from methyl alcohol (cf. Buttle *et al.*, *Biochem. J.*, 1938, 32, 1101). Similarly a sodium salt solution of *p*-acetaminobenzene sulphinic acid in molar amount of 2 : 4-dinitrochlorobenzene in alcohol or refluxing for half an hour afforded the corresponding sulphone (XI).

Hydrolysis to 4'-Aminosulphones.—The acetyl derivative (I part) was heated under reflux with 17% hydrochloric acid (5 parts) for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was cooled and neutralised with sodium carbonate. The solid separated was collected and crystallised from water in case of dihydroxy derivative (I) and from a mixture of acetone and alcohol (1 : 1) in case of the dinitro derivative (X). In case of the compound (IV) the reaction mixture was not neutralised, as hydrochloride on cooling separated out.

Methylation of Dihydroxy Compounds.—The acetaminohydroxy compounds were dissolved in sodium hydroxide solution (10%) and the solution was treated with excess of dimethyl sulphate. The whole was refluxed for 1 hour on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in ice water and the precipitate formed was collected and crystallised from alcohol. This on hydrolysis, as above, afforded the free aminosulphones (III) and (VI).

Preparation of Cinnamoyl Derivatives (VII) and (XII).—In the former case the aminosulphone (I) was dissolved in alcohol and in the latter, the compound (X) was dissolved in acetone, and the respective solution was refluxed for about 15 minutes. The cinnamoyl derivative separated was filtered and washed with alcohol.

Preparation of Schiff's Bases—In this case also, dihydroxysulphone (I) was dissolved in alcohol and dinitrosulphone (X) in acetone. The solution thus obtained was refluxed with cinnamic aldehyde (1.25 mole) as well as with salicylaldehyde (1.25 mole) for about 1 hour. In the former case, the anils (VIII) and (IX) separated on concentrating the alcoholic liquor and in the latter, the anils (XIII) and (XIV) were isolated by diluting the acetone solution with alcohol.

The characteristics of various compounds and derivatives, thus obtained, are recorded in Tables I and II.

TABLE I

3:5-Dihydroxy-4-aminodiphenylsulphones

Compound.	General character.	M. p.	Mol. formula and weight.	Nitrogen (%)	
				Found.	Calc.
(I) R.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .NH ₂ OH = OMe	Colorless needles, insoluble in alkali.	165-66°	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ NS (293)	4.84	4.78
(II) R.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ .NH ₂ . HCl.	Colorless crystalline powder, soluble in alkali.	250-51° (decomp.)	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ O ₄ NS HCl (315.5).	4.51	4.44
(III) R.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ .NHAc	Crystals from alcohol, soluble in alkali.	243-44°	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₅ NE (321)	4.65	4.54
(IV) R.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₂ .NH ₂ OH = OMe	Needles from alcohol, insoluble in alkali.	275-76° (decomp.)	C ₁₅ H ₁₇ O ₅ NS (307)	4.72	4.56
(V) R.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .NH.CO.CH. :CHPh	Colorless prisms, insoluble in common solvents but soluble in alkali.	297-98°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₅ NS (395)	3.55	3.54
(VI) R.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .N:CH.CH: CHPh	Fine yellow needles, soluble in acetone and alkali.	216-17°	C ₂₁ H ₁₇ O ₄ NS (379)	3.72	3.69
(VII) R.SO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .N : CH.C ₆ H ₄ . OH (o)	Fine yellow-orange needles, soluble in acetone and alcohol.	235-36°	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₅ NS (369)	3.46	3.77

TABLE II

2:4-Dinitro-4'-aminodiphenylsulphones

Compounds.	General character.	M. p.	Mol. formula and weight	Nitrogen (%)	
				Found.	Calc.
(X) $R'.SO_2.C_6H_4.NH_2$	Orange crystalline substance, soluble in acetone but insoluble in alcohol.	220°	$C_{12}H_9O_6N_3S$ (323)	12.9	13.0
(XI) $R'.SO_2.C_6H_4.NHAc$	Needles with yellowish tinge, soluble in acetone.	231-32°	$C_{14}H_{11}O_7N_3S$ (365)	11.17	11.51
(XII) $R'.SO_2.C_6H_4.NH.CO.CH : CH.Ph$	Pale yellow crystalline powder; slightly soluble in boiling acetone.	253-55°	$C_{21}H_{16}O_7N_3S$ (453)	9.35	9.27
(XIII) $R'.SO_2.C_6H_4.N : CH.CH : CH.Ph$	Red crystalline powder; soluble in acetone; sparingly in alcohol.	187-88°	$C_{21}H_{15}O_6N_3S$ (437)	9.16	9.0
(XIV) $R'.SO_2.C_6H_4.N : CH-C_6H_4.OH(o)$	Yellow crystalline powder; soluble in acetone, sparingly in alcohol.	201-202°	$C_{19}H_{13}O_7N_3S$ (427)	9.54	9.83

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